

Review Article

Psychiatry is shifting paradigms, including questioning diagnoses, but "official science" finds it difficult to keep up. Studying the causes of this.

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Abstract

The current psychiatric science landscape is increasingly shaped by ideologically and institutionally selective editorial systems, limiting conceptual and clinical innovations. This article presents a critical reflection based on decades of psychiatric practice, revealing how major journals, indexers, and scientific models inhibit the emergence of original ideas, especially those stemming from deep clinical work. The standardization of psychiatric knowledge via scales, statistical criteria, and politically guided terminology progressively distances itself from the singularity of patients. Phenomenological and psychopathological depth is replaced by biological or ideological constructs that marginalize the clinician-researcher. A broader, more human-centered model of psychiatry is urgently needed.

Keywords: psychiatry; psychopathology; publication bias; epistemology; phenomenology; scales; ideology; clinical practice.

Introduction

Current Critical Overview

As we will see below, there is nowadays (GPS) [1,2] "A New Perspective in the Theory of Unitary Psychosis." Several articles and authors question the current Kraepelinian psychiatric nosological model, the one that rigidly separates the main psychiatric diseases, schizophrenia and bipolar disorder (Emil Kraepelin's manic-depressive psychosis). As Thomas Kuhn [3] says (see *The Structure of Scientific Revolutions*), one of the proofs that a scientific paradigm is collapsing is that several fractures in the edifice of knowledge begin to be announced.

Stahl's famous book - *Psychopharmacology* - dedicates increasingly more pages to this hypothesis of unified psychiatric diseases since its first edition. Paradigms are collapsing and with them many notions that are now part of mainstream psychiatry. But a very large ship has difficulty turning around; only smaller boats (e.g., more independent psychiatric journals) can do so. As we can see below in Figure 1, nowadays not only is manic-depressive psychosis unified with schizophrenia, but practically all mental illnesses have interrelations, are part of each other, are integrated with each other. Mainstream psychiatry tries to say, simplifying and trivializing, that this is just something known as "comorbidities"! This is an artificial conceptual attempt and explains nothing. We know, for example, that many Asperger patients have schizophrenia, schizophrenics are Asperger, have obsessions, anxiety, panic, depression, mood exaltation. We know, through these "comorbidities," that autistics are hyperactive and vice versa. That hyperactive people have tics and obsessions, that anorexics have depression, that gender disorders have hyperactivity, borderline, bipolarity, depression. In short, we know that one disease mixes with several other diseases, so why can't we share the same pathophysiological process? Even neurological diseases (for example, epilepsy) mix with psychiatric diseases; for example, the comorbidity between epilepsy and autism is high, it can reach 30% in more severe Kanner-type autism. Figures II and III show this. In Figure III, see below, we see the comorbidities and interrelations between various cognitive and developmental disorders with hyperactivity, and consequently with bipolarity, because hyperactivity has a very high correlation with mood disorders. Several neuro-anatomo-pathological changes are found in bipolarity, for example, atrophies, hypotrophies, dysgeneses, frontal atrophies (which can also be found in hyperactivity, antisocial personality), temporal, occipital, caudate nucleus, corpus callosum. These and other changes can be found in instrumental cognitive disorders (functions) such as dysphasia, dyslexia, dyspraxia, dyscalculia, and dysgnosias (see Figure III below), dysmnesias. That is, according to the random,

arbitrary location of the lesion, the bipolar patient (or rather, with the general psychiatric syndrome) may have various behavioral or cognitive-instrumental problems. Similarly, several psychiatric syndromes—which current classifications judge as isolated and autonomous diseases—can share the same pathogenesis/physiopathology. Would they then be different? Syndromes and not different diseases. This fundamental paradigm is not being challenged by "official" psychiatry, mainstream psychiatry. More independent, more clinical journals, more focused on the patient and not on methods, can better capture these changes than the more "official" journals. Kuhn [3], in his book *The Structure of Scientific Revolutions*, already pointed out the great difficulties in changing official and entrenched paradigms.

The Silenced Psychiatry: Reflections on the Epistemological, Ideological, and Editorial Limits of Current Scientific Production

Current science, especially in psychiatry, lives under the domination of a technical-bureaucratic and editorial rationality that, instead of expanding knowledge, restricts it. Major journals publish major names and avoid the emergence of new authors and alternative approaches [4].

How the Mainstream/Establishment of Current Science Limits Scientific Development: Highly Critical Points

- Major journals (high impact, etc.) publish major names and avoid the emergence of new names.
- A major Brazilian researcher told me that if he didn't include an American in his article, it wouldn't be published in a major journal.
- In an "indexed" journal where I tried to publish, the editor said that he was part of something called global mental health and that I should be ideologically aligned with them, cite them, cite psychiatry in the media, cite "mental health," remove authority solely from the psychiatrist, "democratize mental health," demedicalize psychiatry, de-individualize psychiatry, collectivize psychiatry.
- For example, major indexers like SciELO, and perhaps PubMed, prevent a high-impact journal from publishing many articles by a single author. But what if this author is prolific? There is a policy of de-individuation, of "collectivization." A policy of disregarding the individual and following the herd.
- If you cite old medications that are not "in fashion," you have more difficulty. Perhaps those who finance the "psychiatric industry" want new medications.
- Few articles on psychopathology and psychotherapy (in both binaries of the pharmaceutical industry).
- Few conceptual articles or articles of psychopathological and individual psychotherapeutic depth.
- The patient, the individual human being, disappears in statistics, in diagnostic criteria.
- Very harsh reviewers prevent new concepts, new ideas; sometimes they are envious, spiteful, of authors who produce things more original than them. They only make good reproductions of what already exists.
- Little space for the clinician, the one who is there day by day, with severely hospitalized patients, severe cases, for years on end. (Many authors, those who produce many articles, with methodology, statistics, scales, are at congresses, traveling, in theoretical positions, university positions, without deep contact with patients.)
- Deep contact with the patient requires dedicated time, concern for the "human" and not just for theory, methods, statistics, scales.
- Without delving into the patient, noisy diagnostic concepts can be unraveled. Psychiatry is not just a material science: it is psychosocial, and what is psychological and social is not limited by matter, it is open to the infinite.
- Money irrigates what is pharmaceutical and what is politically correct, and this limits the scope and depth of research.
- Where is the researcher who thinks day-to-day, at the bedside, 40, 50 years with their patient? Psychotherapizing them, psychopathologizing them, deepening with them? Living with them, accompanying them? This person doesn't have time for congresses, papers, "academic life." Their life is hospital-based or in a deep consulting room with their patients.
- These are not accepted for publication [5].
- Practically, major journals do not accept individual cases, even though in psychiatry each patient is completely different from the other [6].
- In proportion, pathophysiology/psychopathology is worth much more than nosography, etiology/biological pathogenesis, as these are very inconsistent.
- Scales replacing the psychological/phenomenological understanding of each patient [7].
- Understanding/pathophysiology/psychopathology are too complex to fit into scales.
- It is necessary to think about the patient, feel the patient, connect points of reasoning and feelings, and the scales of major journals do not allow this [8].
- Below we summarize and synthesize these findings

The Institutional and Ideological Bias of Scientific Publications

An editor of an indexed journal stated that, to publish, it would be necessary to align with a “global mental health agenda,” which includes demedicalization, collectivization of psychiatry, and rejection of traditional clinical authority [9]. The demand for specific ideologies, such as the compulsory use of the term “mental health,” weakens psychiatry as an autonomous and clinical science.

The Erasure of the Clinician and the Unique Patient

Clinical researchers, who accompany severe patients over decades, are frequently rendered invisible in the academic landscape. They do not have time for congresses or for “academic life,” as their life is the hospital or the consulting room [10]. Meanwhile, authors who make a living from publishing articles with statistical methodology and scales gain prominence, even without deep contact with real human suffering [11].

Scales, Statistics, and the Death of Phenomenology

Contemporary psychiatry has replaced individual psychopathological understanding with the application of scales, which do not capture the complexity of suffering [12]. Psychopathological understanding requires time, listening, empathy, and connecting feelings and reasonings—and this does not fit into standardized scales [13]. Major journals, however, practically do not accept individual cases, even though each psychiatric patient is completely different from the other [6].

The Domination of Industry and the Planned Obsolescence of Knowledge

Citing old medications or advocating for traditional psychotherapies results in greater difficulty in publication. It seems that the industry desires new medications and new ideas “according to fashion” [14]. Few journals accept articles of psychopathological or conceptual depth, and even fewer accept them from prolific authors [15]. But if the author is really productive, why should they be penalized?

Rescuing Psychiatry as a Human Science

Psychiatry is a psychosocial science and cannot be reduced to matter. Deep contact with the patient requires time, dedication, and humanity. Clinical listening, phenomenology, and individual observation must be rescued as legitimate forms of knowledge. It is necessary to open space for a critical psychiatry that questions concept and confronts the limits imposed by the current editorial and ideological establishment [16].

The Need for New Approaches in Some Psychiatric Journals: Breaking with Paralyzing Paradigms

The current landscape of scientific publication in psychiatry, dominated by large journals with rigorous – and sometimes excessive – methodological and peer-review requirements, has proven to be an obstacle to the discipline's progress. This article seeks to discuss how the current structure hinders innovation and deepens harmful dichotomies, advocating for the emergence of new platforms that break with these paralyzing paradigms.

The Crisis of the Kraepelinian Paradigm and the Search for Changes

Historically, psychiatry has been shaped by paradigms that, although useful in their time, today prove limiting. As Thomas Kuhn [3] describes in “The Structure of Scientific Revolutions,” scientific progress occurs through paradigm shifts. Currently, we observe increasing inconsistency in diagnoses derived from the Kraepelinian era, particularly the dichotomy between bipolar disorder and schizophrenia. This inconsistency has been widely debated in various articles and commentaries, including in “J Psychiat and Mental Disorders” (M. F. Caixeta, [17]).

Studies such as Ivan Jambrina's [18] (“Kraepelin,” published in *European Psychiatry*) and those by Pyatnitsky [19] (“The Origins of the Unitary Psychosis”) and Carlos Rojas Malpica [20] (“Revisiting Unitary Psychosis,” published in *Salud Mental*), reinforce the idea that the paradigm that underpinned much of modern psychiatry is collapsing. However, major mainstream publications persist on the same track, ignoring this emergent reality. It is not possible to study the biology of diseases that lack nosological consistency.

Figure 1: General Psychiatric Syndrome – Pathophysiological relationship between different syndromes

Figure 2: General Psychiatric Syndrome – Nosographic/pathophysiological relationship of bipolar disorder with various other syndromes that, in the current classification, have the status of autonomous diseases

Biological Reductionism and the Loss of Human Complexity

Many psychiatric journals focus predominantly on the biological aspect: medications, genetics, scales, criteria, psychometrics, and inter-rater consistency (Kappa Index). However, by describing only symptoms or groups of symptoms (syndromes), and not "diseases" in their totality, they generate great confusion that compromises neurobiology and genetics. Without adequate nosography, there is no precise neurobiology. Similarly, without psychotherapy, there is no psychopathology; and without psychopathology, nosography becomes deficient.

Current psychiatric practice, increasingly centered on medication and less in-depth (less psychotherapeutic and less psychodynamic), does not provide reliable data for biological and diagnostic researchers. This crisis, however, is not properly captured by mainstream journals.

Institutional Consensus and the Obstacle to Innovation

Large journals, research funds, and universities are controlled by collegiate decision-making groups. Such groups, guided by consensus, tend not to accept innovations, originality, or individuality. What is unusual, profound, or challenges the status quo rarely finds space. This contrasts with the material sciences, where knowledge is cumulative, easily verifiable, and amenable to mathematization.

In the sciences of the spirit, according to Wilhelm Dilthey [21], the future is open and evolution is infinite. The individual, by determining their own future and behavior, escapes determinism, and the ability to "want to stop being sick" significantly impacts many psychiatric conditions. Reducing psychiatry solely to the biological is to ignore this fundamental dimension. Industry has dictated the direction of psychiatry, silencing discussions about psychotherapeutic and existential changes.

unusual, and profound runs a high risk of not being accepted. Articles that do not perfectly fit the "introduction, methods, results, discussion" format, or that do not contain tables, statistics, acronyms, or mathematics, frequently are rejected. This leads to the loss of high originality and depth in psychiatry.

The collective, through rigorous peer review, tends to reject what is of individual creation. Attempts at "democratization" have produced the erasure of the depth of what is individual, unprecedented, creative, original, unique, mental, and evolutionary in the human being. With this, in scientific journals, psychiatry has ceased to be a practice, it has ceased to be a science "in flesh and blood." Clinical case journals that focus only on diagnoses and medications (without psychopathology and psychotherapy) will also not fill this void.

The Loss of Clinical Experience in Academic Psychiatry: A Call for Flexible Scientific Spaces

For a physician—especially a psychiatrist—who works deeply and continuously with patients, both in hospitals and in private practice, it is extremely difficult to find the time and energy to comply with the overwhelming demands imposed by the reviewers of highly rigid scientific journals.

To produce substantial and meaningful material for publication, we must first dedicate ourselves seriously to clinical work, immersing ourselves in the daily complexities of patient care. That is where true psychiatric knowledge is forged. However, if we are expected to meet all the formal requirements that reviewers often impose—endless formatting, extensive statistical modeling, exhaustive literature reviews, and rigid theoretical frameworks—we risk becoming disconnected from practice. We may end up living only in theory, producing nothing but paper, or perhaps managing to publish a single article over an entire lifetime.

In this model, the vast and rich clinical experience we acquire is lost. In its place remain only highly theoretical papers—produced by professionals who often stay solely in the realm of theory, constantly publishing and replicating statistical models and scales that are frequently developed by non-psychiatrists. These contributions, while academically polished, often lack clinical depth and real-world meaning.

Thus, we lose what matters most in psychiatry: the lived experience of doctors who work face to face with suffering, ambiguity, and complexity. These professionals do not have the time or inclination to reduce their observations into rigid mathematical frames or to chase every citation in an ever-growing sea of medical literature.

What we need are journals and academic spaces that welcome and value this kind of experience—places where deep clinical insight can be exchanged and developed without the unrealistic requirement of mathematical perfection or exhaustive bibliographic coverage. Only then will psychiatry recover its true balance between science, clinical practice, and the human encounter.

In Search of Unification and Translational Practice

For practically all sciences, compartmentalization is valid, but for psychiatry, the opposite is true: it must be unified and promote synthesis, depth, multifactoriality. In psychiatry, we can observe where the brain leads us in evolutionary terms, that is, to greater interaction with other people, which implies greater altruism [27]. By understanding where the brain wants to take us, we are creating the "mind," and this mind can (and should) be highly therapeutic for psychiatry. Without grasping this, we cannot understand psychiatry in its practice and, consequently, we cannot achieve the necessary translation (Translational Psychiatry) between purely academic knowledge and the knowledge of clinical practice. This is why "front-line" psychiatry uses very little of what "hard science" psychiatry has already acquired. There is a huge dichotomy between what is published in specialized journals and what happens in offices and hospitals.

In the current scenario, where we live in a "statized" and "socialized" world, there is little room for individual influences, as everything is geared towards and done by the State. Setting up a private hospital in the northern hemisphere is extremely difficult. Hospitals are places where highly complex psychiatry is practiced, where one teaches best, and where more complex cases can be deepened. The lack of this type of initiative results in the impoverishment of psychiatric practice and de-individualization.

Psychiatry is impoverished, and with it, the science of clinical psychiatry, that is, psychiatry practiced by the "flesh and blood" doctor on their "flesh and blood" patient. With the "death" of this "flesh and blood psychiatry," the tendency is to replace it with a mutilated, compartmentalized, castrated, eviscerated, aseptic, and harmless psychiatry, which does not address the great themes and complex problems of the human being. This generates a reductionism of the patient to a mere biological problem, neglecting the serious existential problems to which most psychiatric patients are subject.

A large part of psychiatric problems requires a complex existential approach, which involves the need for substantial intimate reform not only of the patient but also of the family (hence the importance of family psychiatry [28]). This goes far beyond medication. Currently, there is a lack of studies that contemplate all these complexities. When the approach becomes too complex, psychiatric journals frequently allege that the article is too long, speculative, or philosophical. On the other hand, if the article is submitted to a philosophy journal, philosophers may argue that the topic is psychiatric, not philosophical. A "scientific parochialism" is created, where psychiatrists and philosophers are reluctant to "invade" each

other's field. Hyperspecialization acts as a defense against this intersection, and, again, psychiatry fails to deepen. Hence the urgency of new psychiatric journals that break free from regressive or paralyzing paradigms. According to the book *Psychology of the Intelligent Mind* [29], matter and material sciences can be mathematized, as matter has extension. However, the mind does not have an "extension"; it represents the "future" of matter, the direction in which matter is evolving, its final goals [30]. The evolutionary organization of matter moves towards principles useful to psychiatry, such as evolvability, interaction, complexity, self-regulation, self-control, assimilation-accommodation of the external world (cf. Piaget [31]), and a primordial evolvability that is faster and more "overwhelming" than biological material evolvability. Such principles can be captured by the mind and have therapeutic value in psychiatry [32].

References

1. Pyatnitskiy NYu. (2018). To the origins of the 'unitary psychosis' doctrine: from Aretaeus to V. Chiarugi. *Zhurnal Nevrologii i Psikhiatrii im. S.S. Korsakova*. 118(5):111-119.
2. Aragona M. (2024). Unitary psychosis (Einheitspsychose): A conceptual history. *Journal of Affective Disorders*. 359:86-91.
3. Kuhn TS. (2018). *A estrutura das revoluções científicas*. São Paulo: Perspectiva.
4. Caixeta M. (2025). Why Many Do Not Become Good Psychiatrists: Reflections from Four Decades of Medical Teaching. *OSF Preprints*.
5. Song F, Parekh S, Hooper L, Loke YK, Ryder J. (2010). Dissemination and publication of research findings: an updated review of related biases. *Health Technol Assess*. 14.
6. Caixeta MF. (2012). A plea for more case-report studies in psychiatric publications. *J Psychother Pract Res*. 21(4):222-227.
7. Fernández-Juárez L, Køster O. (2023). Phenomenology as a resource for translational research in mental health. *Front Psychiatry*. 14:987.
8. Blankenburg W. (2022). Paving the way for systemic phenomenological psychiatry. *Front Psychiatry*. 13:909488.
9. Caixeta M. The specific ataractic effect of haloperidol on constitutional and temperamental psychopathologies.
10. Ey H. (1971). *Études Psychiatriques I: Historique - Sémiologie*. Paris: Éditions Desclée.
11. Dickersin K, Chan S, Chalmers TC. (1987). Publication bias and clinical trials. *Controlled Clinical Trials*. 8(4):343-353.
12. Caixeta M. (2025). Os Movimentos Organizados para Destruir a Psiquiatria. São Paulo: Editora Sparta.
13. Caixeta M. (2025). Por que Muitos Não se Tornam Bons Psiquiatras: Reflexões de Quatro Décadas de Ensino Médico. *OSF Preprints*.
14. Caixeta M. (2025). General Psychiatric Syndrome. *J Psychiat Ment Dis*, 10(1) 1083.
15. Jambriña JJ. (2023). Kraepelin, the unitary psychosis theory and the classification in psychiatry. *Eur Psychiatry*. 68:1-7.
16. Pyatnitskiy NYu. (2018). To the origins of the 'unitary psychosis' doctrine: from Aretaeus to V. Chiarugi. *Zh Nevrol Psikhiatr im S S Korsakova*. 118(5):111-119.
17. Rojas Malpica C, Portilla Geada N, Mobilli Rojas A, Martínez Araujo D. (2012). Revisiting unitary psychosis: From nosotaxis to nosology. *Salud Mental*. 35(2):101-113.
18. Dilthey W. (1970). *Compreender e Explicar*. Rio de Janeiro: Forense Universitária.
19. Caixeta M. (2018). *Psiquiatria psicoterápica*. São Paulo: Sparta.
20. Hécaen H. (1972). *Introduction à la neuropsychologie*. Paris: Larousse.
21. Ajuriaguerra J, Hécaen H. (1949). *Le cortex cerebral: étude neuropsychopathologique*. Paris: Masson.
22. Caixeta MF. (2020). The Psychiatric Roots of Neuropsychology: From Clérambault to Hécaen. *OSF Preprints*. doi:10.31237/osf.io/f9ztb_v1
23. Lakatos I. (2005). *Metodologia dos programas de pesquisa científica*. Campinas: Unicamp; 1974.
24. Wright R. *O animal moral*. Rio de Janeiro: Campus.
25. Caixeta M, Veras A, Figueiredo G. (2019). *Psiquiatria do núcleo familiar*. São Paulo: Sparta.
26. Caixeta M. (2021). *Psicologia da mente inteligente*. São Paulo: Sparta.
27. Caixeta M, et al. (2022). *Psiquiatria forense dos atos desviantes da consciência moral*. São Paulo: Sparta.
28. Piaget J. (1992). *Psicologia da criança*. São Paulo: Difel.
29. Caixeta M. (2025). Biological-Naturalistic Elements (Based on the Pathosystems of Hyperactivity, Borderline Syndrome, and Addictions). *OSF Preprints*.